

CULTURAL SCIENCES

ACTIVITY OF THE NATIONAL LIBRARY UNDER MARTIAL LAW: SOCIOCULTURAL ASPECT

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Abstract

The role of the national library in country life is important as a given, and during the wartime, it increases and changes its activity directions. During wartime the libraries face new tasks in the scientific informational field, particularly in teaching and popularising the history of Ukraine, our country's defence stance, and the postwar rebuilding. Using modern technologies, it is possible to direct multiple types of informational activity and bring such work to an appropriate level.

Keywords: national library, sociocultural center, sociocultural activity, innovative activity, scientific informational activity, modern technologies, martial law.

It has been almost two years already since the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation against Ukraine started, and libraries, museums, scientific and educational institutions, and cultural landmarks are being destroyed. Today, one of the pressing topics is the defence of library buildings and funds, as well as the formation of groups for internal work organisation. People with reliable Internet connection have started an active campaign on the information frontlines.

The course of the war and its consequences on the public life and scientific work have brought major changes to work of V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine (VNLU), particularly to the sociocultural department. The lack of traditional information on VNLU's usual activities can be explained by the necessity to inform the readers of the actions of the terrorist state, particularly from the end of February 2022 throughout to the end of May 2022. The informational work back then had been consciously shifted to two chief topics: our reaction to the unexpected and baseless invasion of the enemy, our corresponding actions, as well as the numerous cases of VNLU's international colleagues, libraries, professional unions, numerous friends, and others. VNLU constantly informed its users about financial support for scientists, for Ukrainian startups, giving opportunities for taking part in international contests, internships, receiving grants, stipends, work opportunities in the EU, etc. Due to the statewide martial law implementation, VNLU was able to open its doors only on 12 September 2022. However, it never stopped informing its users about the work done. All of the possible means to do so were used, for example, VNLU's official web page (<http://www.nbu.gov.ua/>) and its Facebook page (https://www.facebook.com/Vernadsky.Library/?local_e=uk_UA). Systemised information fully highlighted the activities done in VNLU.

During the same time, the role and value of sociocultural activity increase, and its success and efficiency positively influence the role of the library in society. Such work is aimed at describing and popularization of traditional, digital information resources; information support of fundamental, applied, scientific research; strengthening of national self-identification, increasing interest in the history of Ukraine, giving the library users opportunities to realise their informational and spiritual needs [1, 2].

Special attention is paid to one of the popular today remote forms of sociocultural activity of VNLU – virtual exhibitions, which have become an important form of popularising the multiversal fund of VNLU during wartime. Exhibition activities is one of the chief sociocultural communication means. They may be categorised into book-archival and fiction-art exhibitions. Most of the book-archival exhibitions are thematically organised, they may be about the present events, dedicated to the commemoration of significant events, the commemoration of important dates, celebration of international and national holidays [3, 4].

However, the war has brought changes to the exhibition activity of VNLU in recent years. In order to inform the users about the occupational war, librarians have prepared and presented on VNLU official site digital book exhibitions, mostly on the military topics: “Education and distance learning in Ukraine under martial law (legislative, governmental, departmental documents)”, “Social and legal protection and psychological assistance during crisis situations. Recommendations and advice during wartime.”, “Military aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine in the context of international humanitarian law: bibliography (1954–2022.)”, “Antirussian sanctions and embargo (2014–2022) in the context of international public law and world experience”, “Anatomy of Russian-Ukrainian conflict (2014–2022) in the era of hybrid wars”, “The phenomenon of the benevolence of Canadian

Ukrainians: at the service of their own people”, “Volunteering”, “Energy security of Ukraine”, “International investments and their role in the economy development of Ukraine”, “Civil protection of the people”, “Aviaindustry of Ukraine: history and modernity.”

Commemorating the year of Russian invasion in Ukraine and the 200th anniversary of the first detailed map of Snake Island, the exposition “Snake Island. Ukraine” was held. Overall, starting in October 2022, book exhibitions of VNLU are exhibited both traditionally and digitally.

Libraries of the National Academy of Sciences (NAS) scientific research institutions have also joined this particular type of activity. For example, from late May to early June 2023 the Paton Institute of Electric Welding hosted an exhibition for defence research and projects of NAS institutions, in which VNLU participated and was awarded a Diploma of the National Academy of Sciences.

In February Ukraine commemorated the tragic one-year anniversary of the full-scale invasion. It was a dramatic and heroic year of resistance. Ukrainians have been fighting for the right to be independent, to have our own state, own history and distinctive culture. On 15 March 2023, VNLU together with Kyiv National University of Technologies and Design presented a photo exhibition of student contest works “The Date”. There were presented both on-camera and smartphone snapshots from the life of those first months of the full-scale invasion. 24 February 2022 turned from a day into a year. The exhibition hosted over 120 photos by 17 authors, students and professors of the “Artistic Photography” department. VNLU and the Professional College of Kyiv National University of Technologies and Design have had fruitful cooperation over many years. The artspace of VNLU is always open to art initiatives and is happy to host participants and visitors (<http://www.nbu.gov.ua/node/6109>).

Today the library has become a center not only of information, where you can study all publicly available reliable digital information resources, but also a space for various events. Despite the war, the library helps to develop the informational space.

During the International Scientific Conference “Library. Science. Communication. Current Issues of Preservation and Innovation of Scientific Libraries” which was held on 4th October 2023, the Poster project of the design group “Creative Resistance” was presented. It was a creative project titled “We Had War for Breakfast”. Based on the platform of the popular messenger Telegram, young graphic designers under the watchful eyes of their professors, started creating anti-war patriotic posters, sending them to the frontlines, and organised exhibitions to present all over Ukraine and abroad. They worked restlessly day and night – in bomb shelters, evacuation trains, with no central heating or electricity, after curfew, while being on the occupied territories, etc. The chief topic of their works is the heroism of AFU, the cruel and cunning nature of RF armies, the demand for support of the international community and NATO, the protection of cultural monuments, positive and negative faces of war.

An important part of sociocultural activity during wartime is cultural and art events, as they help with mental rehabilitation. This last spring the Music Hall in VNLU resumed its work. For over 30 years, various music events have been held in the reading hall of the Music funds Department of VNLU. This tradition began in 1991, and throughout 2000-2019 over 300 concerts were held.

The priority task of VNLU is making sure that its sociocultural work is what the citizens of Ukraine require in their search for information, raising the morale of society, spreading knowledge and providing free access to sources of spiritual heritage. The celebration of Vyshyvanka Day is a long-standing tradition in V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine. Today, the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation has consolidated people, and strengthened the love to our country, the national identity and the unity. The library staff dress every year in vyshyvankas, the traditional embroidered shirt. And just before Vyshyvanka Day, in VNLU there was presented an exhibition of the unique art style of Petrykivka painting: “Petrykivka - the soul of Ukraine”. Petrykivka painting is a Ukrainian decorative and ornamental folk painting, which developed in Dnipropetrovsk region in Petrykivka village over a century ago. Petrykivka painting is listed in the List of intangible cultural heritage list of UNESCO.

Art has always played an important role in cultural development and it has always showcased the morale of the nation. So it is no coincidence that on 9th June 2023 the exhibition titled “Colours of Life” was presented in VNLU, as it is a major cultural institution and an intersection point of the past and present. The exhibition showcased 42 paintings in different art styles. Their authors are Anna Estet, Anastasia Osmolovska, Anastasia Samburska, Katrin Savych, Tosia Kravtsova, Natali Kato, Zhenia Machkovska, and Nadia Khart. The artists hold a dialogue with the viewer, telling them about complex matters that need thinking over through striking colourful art pieces.

Today the sociocultural activity of the library is in the era of developing new concepts and models for more active communication with society; the search for new forms of effective knowledge propagation, scientific achievements, useful information, the development of better communication between society members; and their involvement into the network of traditional and digital library communication [5].

Overcoming major challenges and threats, even in wartime, VNLU still remains the heart of intellectual freedoms and civic activism, a leader of national ideas and European values, a centre for science, culture and education; its mission is the same – to protect the national heritage it stores (manuscripts, printed and digital books, audio and visual media). “The chief task lies in safeguarding this heritage, in physical and digital media, as it is the heritage of many generations of Ukrainian people, and to make it accessible to all the readers, and to integrate into the worldwide informational networks” [6].

V. I. Vernadskyi National Library of Ukraine is open for cooperation and aid. This is largely facilitated by the implementation of new information technologies

and the high professional level of employees. It is important to note that under martial law VNLU functions as a digital institution, continuing the scientific research work, scientific information, scientific publishing, sociocultural and library works, and it spreads important information. Under such hard conditions, the library is a vital institution both for the state and the people as a scientific informational and sociocultural center, developing traditional and implementing innovative activity directions.

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